

INDIA-US RELATIONS : OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

India's foreign policy toward the United States is the result of a unique historical context in which numerous politicians, ambassadors, army personnel, and Indian Diaspora have made significant contributions. This historical background has impacted the development of many principles and concepts in India's foreign policy with the United States to a large extent. India is the world's largest democracy, according to American policymakers, and hence the logical partner of the world's greatest democracy, the United States. One of India's most notable characteristics is its democracy.

Keywords : Foreign Policy, Global Politics, Latin America

Introduction

India and the United States of America are both democratic big players, yet they have vastly different strategic and economic power positions in world affairs. Both historically and socially, the two countries have a lot in common. When India gained independence after WWII, the United States of America was establishing itself as a superpower with military and economic powers. Being the world's two largest democracies, the two were expected to have a tight relationship. However, their relationship began on a shaky footing, and has since seen ups and downs. The fundamental reason for this is a combination of variables, including India's perception of the Western world and the American small nation, big power' syndrome. During the Cold War, these linkages were unable to develop in the desired manner due to ideological reasons. However, after the 9/11 terrorist attacks in the United States, bilateral ties have grown increasingly essential in the twenty-first century. Since then, the two countries have collaborated politically, economically, and strategically. India's new government, led by Narendra Modi, has displayed exceptional

maturity in dealing with Donald Trump's administration on a variety of topics.

India's growing global influence and placement in the Western Hemisphere has necessitated a greater understanding of the Latin American region's strategic importance in India's foreign policy. On the other hand, Latin America's recent global positioning and financial rearrangement, with Brazil's increasing weight as a so-called rising power, exercising an increasingly major influence over the structure of the global political economy and taking dominance in its region. The emergence of emerging economies shows not just their increasing contribution to the global economy, but also the need for deeper ties between emerging and developed economies.

The 7th BRICS Summit, which took place in Ufa, Russia in July 2015 and was attended by the leaders of the BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa), should be taken more seriously as a global force. This symbolises the beginning of a new era in India-Latin America relations, as well as increased Indian engagement in the region.

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Increased economic ties between these two countries over the last decade have resulted in a four-fold rise in trade and investment, making India the United States' eleventh largest trading partner. Despite the fact that trade and investment are at the heart of the Indo-US strategic dialogue, such cooperation in its current form lacks focus, and actual trade has been much below potential, considering the two nations' size and complementarity.

Historical Perspective

After WWII, the United States of America had established itself as a global superpower. Whereas, as a newly independent country, India was focused on nation-building and dealing with challenges of colonialism and imperialism. These programmes had instilled in the minds of US policymakers various misconceptions about India.

The Cold War began to influence international politics in the 1950s, and the United States established bilateral and multilateral security and economic agreements with countries in Western Europe and Asia under the 'one point common programme,' which was based on the containment of communist ideology throughout the world. On the other hand, India openly confirmed its belief in the non-alignment policy and began to consider a pan-Asian society. In the minds of US foreign policymakers, this presented a severe strategic issue.

Furthermore, India's approach toward China was also to blame for the shaky start, as it caused tension in the minds of US authorities and impeded bilateral relations. Apart from that, the Korean conflict and the United States' Pakistan policy have also hampered India-US relations.

The 1965 Indo-Pak war provided the budding partnership between India and the United States a new direction.

However, as the Indian Ocean had become a new battleground between two Super Powers, the United States established a military base at Diego Garcia and stationed its naval sub-marine 'Polaris A-3' here, to which India reacted forcefully and opposed such hostile activities on every international platform. This caused a

rift in bilateral relations between India and the United States. Apart from that, India and the United States have taken different approaches to the Non-Proliferation Treaty. The United States has accused India of being at the root of the problem. America took an anti-India posture in the United Nations and wanted to use force against India. All of these difficulties resulted in a void in bilateral ties.

However, in the 1970s, the United States gave financial assistance to India by implementing the P.L.-480 rule of economic policy. Even US Secretary of State Henry Kissinger paid a visit to India, and a joint commission was formed to improve economic, trade, research, technological, educational, and cultural ties. However, the picture was not as rosy as it appeared, since India's atomic nuclear test of 'Pokhran' and the United States' refusal to ship fuel to the 'Tarapur Thermal Power' plant in response were the main roadblocks to stronger bilateral relations in both countries.

Prime Minister Manmohan Singh and President Bush issued a joint statement on the topic during President Bush's 2006 visit to India, and in 2007, both nations finalised the famous '123 accords' on atomic energy. President Obama visited India twice during his second term, attempting to rebalance the relationship in the correct way. India-US relations have been steadily improving under the Modi administration. The visit of Prime Minister Narendra Modi to the United States in 2014 yielded positive results in bilateral relations. President Barack Obama's reciprocal visit for the Republic Day ceremony was a huge success in terms of establishing ongoing relations. Donald Trump inherited a robust and thriving relationship between India and the United States.

The Trump administration has a favourable stance toward India, particularly in light of its actions against Pakistan, such as the suspension of \$300 million in aid. As a result, despite some points of concern, overall relations between India and the United States have improved since Trump took office. As a result, both countries' foreign policymakers are expected to do everything possible to elevate the bilateral partnership to new heights.

India and Latin America

After the economic meltdown of 2008, growing Latin American economies such as Brazil were forced to reconsider their strategic importance, and Latin America became more recognised as a rising regional and economic power in a multipolar world. The strategic relevance of Latin America to India has risen dramatically in recent decades. The region is rising as one of the fastest-growing economies, and India's cooperation with the region in various forums on trade agreements is critical to India's strategic interests. This partnership has the potential to boost both the Indian and Latin American economy in the long run.

Aside from commerce and business, Latin America has a lot more to offer India in terms of energy, knowledge transfer, and multilateral collaboration on issues like climate change and the environment. In forums such as BRICS (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa), BASIC (Brazil, South Africa, India, and China), and IBSA (India, Brazil, and South Africa), Brazil and India have already collaborated. While India has preferential trade agreements with Chile and the MERCOSUR, it has no free trade agreements with any Latin American or Caribbean countries. Because of the great size of India's middle class, India presents a huge export possibility for Latin America. Beyond exports, India has a well-developed tech sector, service industry, and educational and innovative products from which Latin American countries might benefit.

India continues to be afflicted by a severe energy shortage, which is impeding the country's capacity to enhance its manufacturing industry and expand its economy.

Fortunately, the Western World is one of the world's most energy-rich regions. Because of the recent energy boom in the United States, countries such as Mexico, Colombia, and Trinidad & Tobago are looking for new markets to sell their oil and natural gas. Latin America boasts one of the cleanest electricity grids in the world, in addition to fossil fuels.

As they work to alleviate their energy problem, Latin America and India's green energy capacities could be an area of cooperation.

Opportunities

Renewable energy is critical for both India's and Latin America's long-term viability, and it offers the prospect of future clean-energy collaboration. Suzlon Energy Ltd, an Indian wind energy business, was awarded a project in northeast Brazil in 2006. Brazil and India might extend beyond wind projects into ethanol, an area in which Brazil has significant competence, and solar energy, an area in which Argentina has significant potential. More than 70% of India's oil and gas is imported, with Venezuela becoming a major contributor in the last decade. ONGC Videsh, Indian Oil Corp, and Oil India have bought a 40% share in Carabobo-1, a huge Venezuelan oil field. Reliance Industries, India's largest private offshore production company, has formed a long-term cooperation with Mexico, Venezuela, Ecuador, and Brazil to purchase crude oil. Despite its abundant indigenous coal reserves, India imports coal. Colombia is a top priority for Coal India Limited when it comes to mine acquisitions.

Brazil, for example, is an agriculture superpower with not only vast swaths of fertile land, but also cutting-edge food technologies. Argentina is a pioneer in agricultural research as well. In the next days, the two sides are expected to establish further collaborative enterprises and research collaborations. In recent years, Latin America has also emerged as a major supplier of hydrocarbons for India, accounting for roughly 10% of the country's energy imports. India and Brazil are planning to expand their collaboration in the field of environmentally friendly ethanol. Venezuela, Colombia, Mexico, and Cuba are some of the region's major oil suppliers to India. Over the previous decade, the India-LAC business connection has grown significantly and continues to grow. Bilateral commerce has grown from a low of US\$2 billion in 2000 to a high of US\$46 billion in 2012. This represents a 20-fold growth in trade links between the two countries. India should work to diversify and expand its trading basket with the Latin American and Caribbean region.

There has been a tremendous increase in the provision of better consular assistance, such as faster visa issuance, which is a must for any business transaction.

Forums such as the CII India-LAC Conclave Valedictory in December 2013 have taken the initiative and made a concerted effort to reach out to the LAC countries, particularly business houses and other companies, so that businesses on both sides can see for themselves the immense opportunities that are available between India and the LAC region.

One of the high points of South-South Cooperation is the collaboration between India and Latin America. Rambaxy Laboratories Limited was the first Indian firm to receive approval for a facility in Brazil, and it distributes pharmaceuticals through subsidiaries in Mexico and Peru. India and Latin America have begun working together on the development of antiretroviral medicines (ARVs) to treat HIV/AIDS. India has traditionally been a major supplier of antiretroviral vaccines to nations that do not develop their own. Brazil now imports raw ingredients from India and produces ARVs for its citizens.

Challenges

America's countries pose a broad and complicated diplomatic challenge. Geographic distance is exacerbated by India's relative lack of historic, cultural/linguistic, and diaspora ties, which it has in some form or another with practically every other region. In the previous two decades, India's economic presence in the region has increased dramatically. However, in terms of trade, India lags behind China, and it has been slower to engage the region culturally and politically. Despite recent progress on many fronts, India, as well as Latin America and the Caribbean countries, confront daunting challenges.

They still have among of the world's highest inequality indexes, as well as major infrastructural, technology, innovation, and competitiveness problems.

Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Costa Rica, Cuba, and Peru are among the nations in America that have profited from increased trade flows with the Asia-Pacific area. However, this commerce is primarily inter-industry, with the region exporting primary commodities and natural resource-based products while importing manufactures of varying technological strengths, restricting the potential for closer economic links between the two

regions. Tariff barriers and transportation costs are the two primary barriers to commerce between the two areas, according to a recent analysis by the Inter-American Development Bank. As a result, one of the most significant variables creating a significant difficulty is the cost of transportation between the two locations.

Conclusion

The emergence of growing economies shows not only their increasing contribution to the global economy, but also the strengthening of links between rising and emerging nations, as evidenced by greater South-South trade, investments, and collaboration. Though Delhi continues to strengthen its economic and investment ties with the United States, it is looking for a more planned, structured strategy. Following recent international developments, India must reassess its regional and international strategic relationships with the United States. Bearing in mind the efforts of other rapidly rising nations in today's modern multi-polar world, such as China's, India must make concerted efforts to strengthen its diplomatic ties and establish a presence in the area.

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